

Recurrence Patterns in High Grade Glioma After Chemoradiotherapy: Insights into Target Volume Delineation and Failure Patterns

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Abstract

Background:

High-grade gliomas are aggressive primary brain tumors with poor prognosis despite multimodal therapy. Most patients develop disease recurrence following standard treatment with surgery, radiotherapy, and temozolomide. Characterizing patterns of failure after contemporary chemoradiotherapy is essential to optimize radiation target delineation and improve clinical outcomes.

Methods:

This retrospective single-institution study included patients with World Health Organization (WHO) grade III–IV gliomas treated with maximal safe resection followed by adjuvant radiotherapy and concurrent/adjuvant temozolomide between January 2012 and December 2016. Recurrence patterns were assessed by co-registering follow-up contrast-enhanced magnetic resonance imaging with original radiotherapy planning datasets. Failures were categorized as central, in-field, marginal, distant, or multicentric based on their relationship to the 60 Gy isodose line. Overall survival (OS) and progression-free survival (PFS) were analyzed using Kaplan–Meier methods.

Results:

A total of 41 patients were included. The predominant pattern of failure was local, with central and in-field recurrences observed in 63.3% of patients. Marginal, distant, and multicentric recurrences occurred in 12.1%, 14.6%, and 9.8% of patients, respectively. Median OS and PFS were 27 months and 12 months. Karnofsky performance status and MGMT promoter methylation were associated with improved OS on univariate analysis, with performance status remaining significant on multivariate analysis.

Conclusions:

Local recurrence remains the predominant pattern of failure in high-grade glioma following standard chemoradiotherapy. Survival outcomes in this cohort were favorable compared with historical series, potentially reflecting the impact of effective salvage strategies, including stereotactic radiosurgery. Karnofsky performance status emerged as the most robust independent prognostic factor for overall survival.

Introduction

High-grade gliomas (HGG) are among the most aggressive primary tumors of the central nervous system, accounting for approximately 2% of all malignancies (1,2). Glioblastoma (GBM), the most common subtype, is associated with a particularly poor prognosis, with a median overall survival of approximately 14–16 months and a 5-year survival rate below 10% (3,4). Established prognostic factors include age, performance status, and molecular characteristics such as O6-methylguanine–DNA methyltransferase (MGMT) promoter methylation (5).

The current standard of care for patients with good performance status consists of maximal safe surgical resection followed by adjuvant radiotherapy with concurrent and adjuvant temozolomide (TMZ) (6). The addition of TMZ to radiotherapy has significantly improved survival outcomes compared with radiotherapy alone; however, recurrence remains nearly the same (7). This highlights a fundamental limitation in current treatment strategies.

A defining characteristic of HGG is its highly infiltrative nature, with tumor cells extending beyond radiographically visible disease into surrounding normal brain tissue. This poses a major challenge for radiotherapy planning, as treatment volumes must balance adequate tumor coverage against the risk of radiation-induced neurotoxicity. Historically, Radiation Therapy Oncology Group (RTOG) guidelines (8) have recommended inclusion of peritumoral edema within the clinical target volume (CTV), resulting in relatively large irradiation volumes. In contrast, European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer (EORTC) (9) guidelines advocate smaller target volumes based primarily

on contrast-enhancing tumor and surgical cavity with limited margins.
(Figure 1)

Figure 1. Radiotherapy target volume delineation on axial brain imaging.

GTV (red dashed), CTV (pink dotted), and PTV (solid pink) contours are shown.

Despite these differing approaches, multiple studies have consistently demonstrated that the predominant pattern of failure in GBM is local, occurring within or adjacent to the high-dose radiation field (10–12). Importantly, reducing CTV margins or omitting peritumoral edema has not been associated with an increased risk of marginal or distant recurrence (10). These findings suggest that treatment failure is unlikely to be solely due to inadequate target delineation or geographic miss.

In this context, a detailed understanding of recurrence patterns in relation to delivered radiation dose is essential to inform rational treatment strategies.

In the present study, we retrospectively analyzed patients with high-grade glioma treated with standard chemoradiotherapy to characterize patterns of recurrence using co-registered imaging and dosimetric analysis. We hypothesized that the predominance of in-field recurrence reflects intrinsic tumor radioresistance rather than inadequate radiation coverage. The aim of this study was to evaluate recurrence patterns following RT-TMZ and to explore their implications for target delineation and treatment optimization.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Population

This retrospective, single-institution study included patients with recurrent high-grade glioma (HGG) treated at the Department of Radiation Oncology, Max Super Specialty Hospital, Saket, New Delhi, India, between January 2012 and December 2016. Eligible patients were aged 18–70 years with a Karnofsky Performance Status (KPS) >50 (13), who had previously undergone radiotherapy with concurrent and adjuvant temozolomide (TMZ) at the same institution.

Patients who received prior radiotherapy outside the institution or had low-grade gliomas (WHO grade I–II) were excluded. A total of 41 patients met the inclusion criteria and were included in the final analysis.

Clinical Characteristics

The median age at diagnosis was 52 years (range, 27–70), with 30 males and 11 females. Surgical resection included gross total resection (GTR) in 29 patients, near-total resection (NTR) in 7, and subtotal resection (STR) in 5. Histopathology revealed glioblastoma (WHO grade IV) in 23 patients and grade III anaplastic glioma in 18 patients.

Radiotherapy Technique

All patients underwent CT simulation in the supine position using a thermoplastic immobilization mask. Planning CT images were co-registered with pre- and postoperative contrast-enhanced MRI for target delineation.

Radiotherapy was delivered to a total dose of 60 Gy in 30 fractions (2 Gy per fraction, 5 days per week) over 6 weeks using a 6-MV photon beam on a linear accelerator (Varian Medical Systems, CA, USA).

Target volumes were defined as follows: (Figure 2)

1. Gross Tumor Volume (GTV): Postoperative residual tumor and resection cavity delineated on T1-weighted contrast-enhanced MRI
2. Planning Target Volume 1 (PTV1): GTV with a 0.5 cm margin (prescribed dose: 60 Gy)
3. Clinical Target Volume (CTV edema): GTV plus peritumoral edema defined on T2/FLAIR MRI (prescribed dose: 55 Gy)
4. Planning Target Volume 2 (PTV2): CTV edema with a 1.5 cm margin (prescribed dose: 54 Gy)

Chemotherapy Protocol

Concurrent chemotherapy consisted of temozolomide at 75 mg/m² daily, administered throughout the course of radiotherapy. Adjuvant TMZ was initiated 4 weeks after completion of radiotherapy and delivered for 5 days every 28 days. The starting dose was 150 mg/m² for the first cycle, escalated to 200 mg/m² from the second cycle onward if tolerated. Dose modifications or treatment interruptions were made in cases of disease progression or grade 3–4 toxicity.

Ethical Approval

This study was approved by the institutional ethics committee. Given the retrospective nature of the study and anonymization of patient data, the requirement for informed consent was waived.

Figure 2. Contouring protocol of GBM of Max Cancer Center

GTV, CTV edema, PTV1 (GTV + 0.5 cm), and PTV2 (CTV + 1.5 cm) are depicted.

Data Collection

Clinical and treatment-related data were retrieved from outpatient department (OPD) records, the treatment planning system, and dose-volume histogram (DVH) records. All data were systematically recorded in a predefined data collection format.

MRI Follow-up and Assessment of Recurrence

The first post-treatment MRI of the brain was performed approximately 2 months after completion of concurrent chemoradiotherapy. Subsequent MRI evaluations were conducted after every two cycles of adjuvant temozolomide. All imaging studies were independently reviewed by two experienced neuroradiologists, and findings were correlated with the patients' neurological status and overall clinical condition.

Radiological progression was defined according to the Response Assessment in Neuro-Oncology (RANO) criteria (14) as either a $\geq 25\%$ increase in the sum of the products of perpendicular diameters of enhancing lesions or the appearance of new lesions or clinical progression.

Recurrence Pattern Analysis

For recurrence pattern analysis, contrast-enhanced MRI scans at the time of progression were co-registered with the original radiotherapy planning CT datasets. The recurrent tumor volume (V_{recur}) was contoured on fused CT-MRI images without prior knowledge of the original treatment volumes to minimize delineation bias.

The spatial relationship between V_{recur} and the 60 Gy isodose line (IDL) was analyzed, and recurrence patterns were classified as follows:

1. Central recurrence: $>95\%$ of the V_{recur} inside the 60-Gy IDL
2. In-field recurrence: 80–95% of the V_{recur} inside the 60-Gy IDL
3. Marginal recurrence: 20–80% of the V_{recur} inside the 60-Gy IDL
4. Distant recurrence: $<20\%$ of the V_{recur} inside the 60-Gy IDL

Pseudoprogression

Pseudoprogression was defined as a transient increase in contrast enhancement occurring within 2–6 months after completion of chemoradiotherapy, followed by spontaneous stabilization or regression on subsequent imaging. In contrast, lesions demonstrating continuous progression on serial MRI were classified as true tumor recurrence.

Recursive Partitioning Analysis (RPA):

Patients were classified according to the RTOG recursive partitioning analysis (RPA) system. In this cohort, 1 patient was classified as RPA class I, 10 as class II, 11 as class III, 15 as class IV, and 4 as class V, with no patients in class VI. For survival analysis, patients were grouped into two categories: RPA I–II and RPA III–V. Overall survival between groups was compared using Kaplan–Meier analysis.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was performed to evaluate survival outcomes and recurrence patterns. Overall survival (OS) was defined as the time from the date of pathological diagnosis to death or last follow-up. Progression-free survival (PFS) was defined as the time from completion of radiotherapy to disease progression or death. Time to recurrence was calculated from the date of diagnosis to radiological evidence of disease recurrence.

Survival outcomes were estimated using the Kaplan–Meier method, and comparisons between groups were performed using the log-rank test. Patients who were alive and without disease progression at the time of last follow-up were censored.

Univariate analysis was performed to assess the association of clinical and pathological factors, including Karnofsky Performance Status (KPS), MGMT promoter methylation status, recurrence pattern, and recursive partitioning analysis (RPA) grouping, with overall survival. Multivariate analysis was conducted using binary logistic regression to identify independent predictors of survival.

Recurrence patterns were reported descriptively as proportions. Progression-free survival was further analyzed according to recurrence pattern (central, in-field, marginal, and distant).

A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant. All statistical analyses were performed using STATA version 11.2 (StataCorp, College Station, TX, USA).

Results

A total of 41 patients with high-grade glioma treated with radiotherapy and concurrent temozolomide (RT-TMZ) between January 2012 and December 2016 were included in the analysis. Baseline characteristics are summarized in Table 1.

All patients were initially planned for radical radiotherapy to a dose of 60 Gy in 30 fractions with concurrent temozolomide. Two patients aged >65 years received hypofractionated radiotherapy (40 Gy in 15 fractions).

Table 1. Characteristics of patients with recurrent high-grade glioma (n=41)

Characteristics	Patients
Gender	
Male	30
Female	11
Types of surgery	
GTR	29
NTR	7
STR	5
Pathological diagnosis	
GBM (Grade IV)	23
Anaplastic astrocytoma (Grade III)	8
Age at diagnosis (years)	
Median	52
Range	27-70
Karnofsky performance status	
Median	80
Range	90- 50
RPA grouping	
RPA Group I	1
RPA Group II	10
RPA Group III	11
RPA Group IV	15
RPA Group V	4
RPA VI	0

Survival Outcomes

At the time of analysis, follow-up data were obtained from medical records and supplemented by telephonic contact. Six patients were alive, and 35 had died.

The median follow-up duration was 24 months. The median overall survival (OS) for the entire cohort was 27 months (Figure 3), with 1-year and 2-year OS rates of 85.3% and 63.4%, respectively. The median progression-free survival (PFS) was 12 months.

The median time to recurrence from completion of radiotherapy was 12 months (range, 3–62 months).

Figure 3: Kaplan-Meier Survival analysis (n = 41)

Recurrence Patterns

The distribution of recurrence patterns is summarized in Table 2, and representative examples are shown in Figures 5–8. Recurrence patterns were determined by co-registering contrast-enhanced MRI at the time of relapse with the original radiotherapy planning CT.

Figure 4. Distribution of pattern of recurrence in percentage (%)

The most common pattern of first recurrence was central, observed in 15 patients (36.5%), followed by in-field recurrence in 11 patients (26.8%), distant recurrence in 6 patients (14.6%), marginal recurrence in 5 patients (12.1%), and multicentric recurrence in 4 patients (9.8%). (Figure 4)

Figure 5. Central recurrence: Total volume of recurrence (V_{recur}) is 8.6 cm^3 Volume inside 60 Gy IDL is 8.4 cm^3 (97%)

Figure 6. Infield- recurrence: Total volume of recurrence is 8.1 cm³
 Volume inside 60 Gy IDL is 7.3 cm³ (90.1%)

Figure 7. Marginal recurrence: Total volume of recurrence is 13.3 cm³
 Volume inside 60 Gy IDL is 9.1 cm³ (68%)

Figure 8. Multicentric recurrence: Central recurrence has 100% volume of recurrence inside 60Gy IDL, Marginal recurrence has 48.2% volume of recurrence inside 60Gy IDL, Distant recurrence has 0% volume of recurrence inside 60Gy IDL

Survival outcomes varied according to recurrence pattern. Patients with central recurrence demonstrated a median overall survival (OS) of 39 months and a median progression-free survival (PFS) of 13 months. The 1-year and 2-year OS rates were 100% and 60%, respectively. (Figure 9)

Patients with in-field recurrence had a median OS of 27 months and median PFS of 12 months, with 1-year and 2-year OS rates of 72.7% and 45%, respectively. (Table 2)

Figure 9. Kaplan- Meier survival analysis by pattern of recurrence

Patients with marginal recurrence showed the longest survival outcomes, with a median OS of 44 months and median PFS of 19 months. The 1-year and 2-year OS rates were 100% and 60%, respectively.

Patients with distant recurrence had a median OS of 20 months and median PFS of 14.5 months, with 1-year and 2-year OS rates of 66% and 50%, respectively.

Multicentric recurrence was observed in 4 patients (9.8%) and was associated with poorer outcomes, with a median OS of 14 months and median PFS of 8.5 months. (Table 2)

Kaplan–Meier analysis demonstrated a statistically significant difference in overall survival across recurrence patterns (log-rank test, $p = 0.018$).

Table. 2. Pattern of recurrence and overall progression free survival (n=41)

Recurrence pattern	Total Number of Cases	Median progression free Survival (PFS) (Months)	Median overall survival (OS) (Months)	Recurrence at 12 Months (n=21)	Recurrence at 24 Months (n=12)
Central	15 (36.5%)	13	39	7 (47%)	5 (33%)
In - Field	11 (26.8%)	12	27	8 (73%)	1 (9%)
Marginal	5 (12.1%)	19	44	1 (20%)	2 (40%)
Distant	6 (14.6%)	14.50	20	2 (33%)	3 (50%)
Multicentric	4 (9.75%)	8.50	14	3 (75%)	1 (25%)

Prognostic Factors and Survival Analysis

1.MGMT Promoter Methylation

MGMT promoter methylation status was available for 23 patients (56%). Among these, 14 patients were MGMT-positive and 9 were MGMT-negative. Patients with MGMT-positive tumors demonstrated improved survival, with a median overall survival (OS) of 39 months compared to 27 months in MGMT-negative patients. This difference was statistically significant (log-rank test, $p = 0.04$). (Figure 10)

2. Karnofsky Performance Status (KPS)

KPS was a significant predictor of overall survival. Patients with KPS ≥ 70 had a median OS of 31 months, compared to 20 months in patients with KPS < 70 (log-rank test, $p = 0.01$). (Figure 11)

Figure 10. Kaplan – Meier survival estimates with MGMT status

Figure 11. Kaplan-Meier survival graph with performance status (KPS)

3. Recursive Partitioning Analysis (RPA)

Patients were stratified according to the RTOG recursive partitioning analysis (RPA) classification. For analysis, patients were grouped into RPA I–II (n = 11) and RPA III–V (n = 30), with no patients in class VI.

Kaplan–Meier analysis demonstrated improved survival in the RPA I–II group, with a median OS of 39 months compared to 27 months in the RPA III–V group. Median progression-free survival (PFS) was 12 months and 12.5 months, respectively. (Figure 12)

Figure 12. Survival analysis according to RPA grouping (I,II vs IV-VI)

4. Other Clinical Factors

There was no significant association between overall survival and extent of surgical resection (gross total, near total, or subtotal resection) ($p = 0.6$). Similarly, preoperative tumor volume and tumor grade (grade III vs IV) were not associated with survival outcomes ($p = 0.26$ and $p = 0.47$,

respectively). Age at diagnosis (<50 vs ≥50 years) was also not a significant predictor of overall survival ($p = 0.29$).

Subependymal recurrence was observed in 13 patients, of whom 7 had local recurrence (central or in-field), 3 had marginal recurrence, 2 developed multicentric recurrence, and 1 had distant failure.

Discussion

In this retrospective cohort of 41 patients with high-grade glioma treated with standard chemoradiotherapy, the predominant pattern of failure was local, with central and in-field recurrences accounting for 63.4% of cases. Marginal, distant, and multicentric recurrences were less frequent, consistent with prior reports demonstrating that disease relapses in high-grade glioma predominantly occurs within or adjacent to the high-dose radiation region (10–12).

Our survival outcomes compare favorably with historical data. The median overall survival (OS) of 27 months and progression-free survival (PFS) of 12 months observed in this study are higher than those reported in landmark trials such as Stupp et al. (median OS 14.6 months, PFS 6.9 months)(15) and other studies reporting OS in the range of 20 months especially with use of tumor treating field (16). A high proportion of patients in our cohort (39 of 41) received salvage stereotactic radiosurgery at recurrence, which may have contributed to the improved survival outcomes observed.

Consistent with existing literature, local recurrence remained the dominant pattern of failure. Previous studies have reported central recurrence rates ranging from 63% to 83%, with relatively low rates of marginal recurrence (10–12). In comparison, the incidence of central recurrence in our study (36.5%) was lower than that reported in most international series, while marginal recurrence (12.1%) was slightly higher but remained within the reported range. Distant recurrence rates (14.6%) were comparable to previously published data (25,35).

A key finding of this study is the relatively lower central recurrence rate, which may be attributable to differences in target volume delineation and dose distribution. In our institutional protocol, the clinical target volume

(CTV) included peritumoral edema treated to a higher dose (54–55 Gy) compared to traditional RTOG-based approaches, where edema typically receives 46 Gy (8). Given that peritumoral edema may harbor infiltrative tumor cells, dose escalation to this region could potentially reduce central failures (17). This hypothesis is supported by the observed lower central recurrence rate and improved survival outcomes in our cohort.

The role of target volume delineation remains an area of ongoing debate. While RTOG protocols advocate larger treatment volumes including edema, European (EORTC) guidelines support smaller margins without compromising outcomes (8,9). In the era of advanced imaging and conformal radiotherapy, the benefit of larger radiation fields is increasingly questioned, particularly given the risk of neurocognitive toxicity associated with irradiation of normal brain tissue (18). Our findings support a more tailored approach to target delineation, balancing adequate tumor coverage with minimization of normal tissue exposure.

Prognostic factor analysis demonstrated that both MGMT promoter methylation status and Karnofsky Performance Status (KPS) were associated with overall survival on univariate analysis. However, on multivariate analysis, KPS emerged as the only independent predictor of survival, consistent with its established role in glioma prognostication and its incorporation into RTOG recursive partitioning analysis models.

Interestingly, factors such as age, tumor grade, extent of resection, and preoperative tumor volume were not significantly associated with survival in this cohort. This may be due to the relatively small sample size, selection bias, and lack of comprehensive molecular profiling, including IDH mutation status, which is now recognized as a critical prognostic factor in glioma classification.

This study has several limitations, including its retrospective design, single-institution setting, relatively small sample size, and incomplete molecular data. Additionally, the high use of salvage stereotactic radiosurgery may confound survival comparisons with other studies.

Conclusion

Local recurrence remains the predominant pattern of failure in high-grade glioma following standard surgery and temozolomide-based chemoradiotherapy. In this cohort, the median overall survival and progression-free survival were 27 months and 12 months, respectively, which compare favorably with historical series and may, in part, be attributable to the high utilization of salvage stereotactic radiosurgery at recurrence. The inclusion of peritumoral edema within the clinical target volume and its treatment to a higher dose (54–55 Gy), compared with conventional RTOG approaches, may also have contributed to the observed lower central recurrence rates. Among evaluated prognostic factors, Karnofsky Performance Status emerged as the most robust independent predictor of overall survival, while MGMT promoter methylation was significant on univariate analysis.

Author Contributions

All authors have reviewed and approved the final version of the manuscript and agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

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